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ENLIGHT RISE- RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA WITH AND FOR SOCIETY: LEVERAGING DIGITAL INNOVATION FOR A GREENER AND HEALTHIER EUROPE

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Data management plan: assessment of data generated and/or existing data used and processed in the frame of ENLIGHT RISE, selection of appropriate and secure repository to make data accessible and re-usable in line with FAIR principles, assessment of full compliance with GDPR for any personal data collection in the frame of the project.

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INTRODUCTION

1.1 Project Summary

ENLIGHT is a European University Network to promote equitable quality of Life, sustainability, and global engagement through Higher education Transformation. It brings together 9 comprehensive, research-intensive, new flagship universities with a strong reputation.

ENLIGHT strives to transform the way in which we address global societal challenges by developing new models and methodologies for education and research adapted to the complex sustainability issues facing cities and communities today. ENLIGHT focuses on five flagship challenges: Health & Well-being, Climate change, Energy & Circular Economy, Digital Revolution and Equity.

With Horizon 2020 SwafS project “ENLIGHT RISE” (Research and Innovation agenda with and for Society), it will be supported in its R&I dimension, to deploy a comprehensive joint transformation agenda, in synergy with the educational component, in partnership with surrounding ecosystems, and with the overarching goal of serving our societal missions.

The objective is to become more competitive and innovative together, leveraging and synergizing our respective strengths and capitalizing on our innovation potential and partnerships with our surrounding ecosystems to jointly promote a greener, healthier, more equitable and sustainable Europe.

To reach these goals, ENLIGHT RISE will:

1. establish a longer-term business model for joint R&I actions;
2. identify strong research synergies with high innovation potential;
3. enable the sharing of and optimize capacity of digital research infrastructures, while benchmarking and optimizing the societal impact of digital innovation/artificial intelligence;
4. reinforce cooperation and co-creation with the business sector and civil society;
5. mainstream and incentivize open science practices and public engagement;
6. improve the attractiveness of researchers' careers;
7. develop and formalize methods towards an impact-driven R&I agenda.

1.2 Executive Summary

The Data Management Plan (DMP) describes the collection, generation, management, documentation, preservation and sharing of data during ENLIGHT RISE project, in compliance with Article 29 of the Grant Agreement Number 101035819 which states mandatory the use of open access to scientific publications (Article 29.2), with the exemption shown in Article 29.3.

The DMP is a living document, which will be updated during the project. The first version was produced in month 6 as deliverable D9.3.

The DMP aims at making Research data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR) and includes:

- *the handling of research data during and after the project ;*
- *the type of data collected, processed and generated by the project ;*
- *the methodology and standards applied ;*
- *whether data will be shared/made open and how ;*
- *how data will be curated and preserved.*

The application of this document is the responsibility of all ENLIGHT RISE project partners. This document will be updated throughout the lifecycle of the project to enrich and update the current information as well as to include new issues or changes in the project procedures.

Any update of the document will follow the internal approval procedures as described in the Consortium Operating Procedures.

This DMP was created using the [DMPonline.be](https://dmponline.be) template for Horizon Europe projects with the following structure:

- *DATA SUMMARY*
- *FAIR DATA*
- *OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUTS*
- *ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES*
- *DATA SECURITY*
- *ETHICS*
- *OTHER ISSUES*

1.3 Data Management Policy

The ENLIGHT RISE consortium has elaborated a Data Management Plan to make sure that the consortium members act according to EU and national regulations, with particular focus on the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 on GDPR. Moreover, all the partners have signed a Data Processing Agreement that clarifies the processing of Personal Data in the Framework of the ENLIGHT Project between them.

The Data management plan includes information on the responsibilities concerning data collection, processing, and storage. It explains the process to be followed by the consortium members to collect and process data, and how to make the data FAIR.

Data Management approach, roles, and responsibilities

To guarantee an appropriate coverage of all data-related aspects and activities, a structured approach has been followed. The data generated and collected along the project implementation has been mapped and defined. The consortium agreed on the most appropriate way to manage them, proportionally to their sensitiveness.

The approach implemented has been structured in 3 main steps:

STEP 1 - LISTING DATA SETS: Under this step, all WP leaders have been requested to fill a summary table and questionnaire template detailing all the different datasets that are expected to be generated or collected per each WP/task and deliverable; in this phase, WP Leaders are responsible to collect from task responsible specific detail per each task and orchestrate this mapping exercise at WP-level; this activity allows the consortium to have a first overview of all datasets to be collected/generated, with preliminary indications on their nature and format, level of sensitiveness (e.g. personal data) and dissemination level (as expected per the DoA).

STEP 2 - CLASSIFICATION OF DATA SETS: Under this step, the University of Bordeaux and Ghent University simplified the data set and propose a structure for the classification of the data sets relevant for the project purposes, based on the inputs collected under; this approach allows to codify a relevant set of data categories and better investigate their level of sensitiveness and to define the most appropriate measures to be taken; for this purpose, the University of Bordeaux and Ghent University also created a template for data set description to be filled by each competent partner in order to have all the information needed to appropriately manage such datasets.

STEP 3 - DATA SET MANAGEMENT: All dataset owners provide detailed information on the datasets to be managed and the intended approach; this information are subsequently reviewed by the University of Bordeaux and Ghent University in order to identify relevant gaps or points of improvement, as well as to harmonize the approach followed by each dataset owner according to the category of data and level of sensitiveness; this classification and codification of progressive data protection levels will allow to avoid any over or underestimation of the data protection measures to be put in place in each case.

The above-described process not only allows to standardize appropriate procedures to deal with data management, but also to define ownerships and responsibilities of all the partners involved in data management.

Within the project, **dataset owners** (as identified in the procedure above) can be considered as **data controllers** according to the definition of the GDPR, which refers to data controllers as *“the natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data”*. Consequently, the dataset owners (i.e. data controllers) will be in charge to:

- implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure and to be able to demonstrate that processing is performed in accordance with GDPR ;
- review and update such measures where necessary ;
- supervise the appropriate implementation of such measures.

Moreover, other partners involved in the activities mapped above by each dataset owner, will be considered as **data processors**, according to the GDPR definition, namely *“a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which processes personal data on behalf of the controller”*. The data processors will have to comply with the approaches and measures defined by the data controller.

1. DATA SUMMARY

1.1 Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for?

Re-use of existing data available from research projects and from other European projects is encouraged in the project. We use strategic plans of each partner university, for benchmarking purposes as well as for analysis for the joint approaches/policies/goals in public engagement. We collect and process data, available through public sources about the performance of each partner in Horizon 2020 (e.g. <https://data.europa.eu/data/datasets/cordish2020projects?locale=en>, Cordis, Lens.org). Moreover, several questionnaires to be filled out by partners, complement the publicly available data. Detailed information can be found in the data table.

1.2 What types and formats of data and other research outputs will the project generate or re-use?

Data is collected in the form of

- surveys
- interviews
- the research systems of the partners
- data from CORDIS,
- etc.

The following formats will be used and transformed where necessary for archiving:

- Text (eg. .txt, .rtf, .doc, .docx)
- Tabular data (eg. csv, .xls, .xlsx)
- Other (eg. JPEG, pdf, xml, por, dwg, ...)

Detailed information can be found in the data table.

1.3 What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?

ENLIGHT RISE will generate and process technical, commercial, and non-commercial data and collect best practices, technical, commercial, non-commercial, and personal data in compliance with all national and EU ethics and legal requirements in the frame of the following activities per WPs:

- WP1: Establish a sustainable business model towards a collaborative R&I agenda.
 - Task 1.1 Analyse and benchmark good practices among ENLIGHT partner research support offices.
 - Task 1.3. Deploy grant/researcher & researcher/researcher digital matching tools.
- WP2: Create synergies through R&I capacity building.
 - Task 2.1.1 Collection of data: We will collect the member universities' scientific and technological profiles (publication, EU grant, and patent data) starting with specialized databases, also involving the technology transfer offices (TTOs), research support offices and libraries of the 9 universities to collect the most representative portfolios.
 - Task 2.1.3 Compare and match the 9 universities' profile based on ENLIGHT flagship challenges: based on the short individual analyses we will produce a report highlight common skills of the 9 universities on shared research topics linked to the 5 flagship challenges.
 - Task 2.2 Set up an ENLIGHT Research & Innovation Observatory (R&I Observatory).
- WP3: Roadmap towards shared digital research infrastructures and responsible DI/AI index.
 - Task 3.1 Mapping, connecting, and enhancing digital research infrastructures in ENLIGHT.

- Task 3.2.3 Develop an ENLIGHT Responsible DI/AI Development Index.
- WP4: Promote early career development & improve researcher assessment.
 - Task 4.1.1 Establish an ENLIGHT early career researcher network.
 - Task 4.2. Benchmark assessment systems of researchers and propose innovations.
- WP5: Roadmap for an ENLIGHT European Innovation District
 - Task 5.1 Map and benchmark academy-industry collaborations in the innovation ecosystem of ENLIGHT
- WP6: Co-create R&I actions with society.
 - Task 6.1 Survey of existing civil society engagement tools and projects in research, innovation, teaching, and learning.
- WP7: Optimize Open Science practices and identify frontiers.
 - Task 7.1. Strengthen and mainstream Open Science practices in ENLIGHT.
- WP8: Impact assessment and frontiers of the common R&I agenda
 - Task 8.1.3 Collect & analyse opportunities and barriers encountered to implement a common impact-driven R&I agenda; these will be used in Task 8.2 to share best practices and jointly find solutions with other EUNs.
 - Task 8.2 Structured collaboration at the European level, among pilot Alliances.
- WP9: Management, Dissemination and Exploitation.
 - Task 9.2. Communication, dissemination and exploitation.

In WP1 and WP2, the purpose of the tool (digital matching tool) and the data generated or re-used will be to improve the collaboration between researchers of the consortium and find funding opportunities to researchers to have more impactful research in the five flagship challenges of ENLIGHT.

Data from other initiatives may be used to amend the information that can be derived from the data collected by WP7 (e.g., EUA surveys on Open Science, OpenAIRE, OpenAPC).

In order to assess if there is progress in ENLIGHT universities impact literacy, as well as WP8's own impact in the promotion of a culture of impact, the data obtained from the different surveys will be reused for comparison purposes. In conformity with the task 8.1.2 objectives, the data collected in the repository is expected to be used and re-used by all project partners in a first moment and then by the wider public at the end of the project.

1.4 What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?

The total volume of data will amount to several GB.

- For WP1 and the Deliverable 1.1: Spreadsheet documents of less than 1 MB; Tabular data of a several MB are expected.
- For WP2, we foresee a more extensive size since we will accommodate all ENLIGHT (RISE) outcome/products/results.
- For WP7, only small datasets are created (spreadsheets in csv format, less than 10 MB).
- For the other WPs, data will be evaluated during the project and will depend on the extend and the nature of the data.

Detailed information can be found in the data table.

1.5 What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?

- Data from ENLIGHT RISE partners, WPs, and research support offices.
- Responses to various surveys, e.g. the Research Impact Literacy Surveys.
- Public information available online and information agreed to be disclosed by project partners.
- Existing research platform, as VialInno based on partners data sources using Scopus and Web of Science, Lens.org, etc.
- The analysis of the performance in Horizon 2020 will be based on data from the public source Cordis.

Detailed information can be found in the data table.

1.6 To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

- ENLIGHT consortium
- European Stakeholders
- Scientific community
- European Commission services and European Agencies
- EU national bodies
- General audience

Data will be useful to ENLIGHT partners (governance and operational levels) and external stakeholders (the quadruple helix) related to the local ecosystems.

In WP1 (benchmark) we treat the data as confidential and will not as such be fully made available to people outside the project since the data describes internal procedures (and trade secrets) of research support offices.

In WP8, both the results of the Research Impact Literacy Surveys and the repository identified practices could be of interest to other universities, networks or organisations working on impact policies and strategies and/ or on impact assessment and measurement methodologies: European ENLIGHT partners & other University Alliances or collaborations.

2. FAIR DATA

2.1 FAIR data: Making data findable, including provisions for metadata.

2.1.1 Will data and other research outputs be identified by a persistent identifier?

- Yes / No

Deliverables and data that will be made publicly available through Zenodo, will have a DOI. Locally stored unpublished data will not have a PID.

Where available, people will be identified with their ORCID.

Detailed information can be found in the data table.

2.1.2 Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

Publicly available datasets and deliverables in Zenodo.org are described following datacite metadata schema, with the following elements:

- Title
- Author
- Date
- DOI
- Keywords
- Description
- Licence
- Funding
- Access level

The R&I observatory uses its own metadata schema, containing the fields university, name, expertise, subthematics, description, keywords, ENLIGHT Flagships, webpage.

Locally stored data use different metadata schema, following the SharePoint schema.

Detailed information can be found in the data table.

2.1.3 Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?

- Yes / No

The description of publicly available outcomes in Zenodo contains keywords.

However, as for the mapping or the R&I observatory keywords are used, linked to the flagship domains and the expertise area of the researcher to facilitate the synergies between actors.

2.1.4 Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

- Yes

The metadata of published data and deliverables in Zenodo can be harvested using the [OAI-PMH Interface](#). Metadata of locally stored outcomes cannot be harvested.

2.2 FAIR data: Making data accessible.

2.2.1 Will the data and other research outputs be deposited in a trusted repository?

- Yes

A Zenodo community has been created to upload publicly available outcomes: <https://zenodo.org/communities/enlight-rise>

2.2.2 Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data and other research outputs will be deposited?

- Yes

ENLIGHT RISE has decided to use Zenodo for publicly available outcomes, which complies with our needs. The use of Zenodo is quite straightforward. No need for more arrangements.

2.2.3 Does the repository ensure that the data and other research outputs are assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Zenodo assigns a DOI.

2.2.4 Will all data and other research outputs be made openly available?

Some data (except financial/contractual and personal data) related to the list below will be uploaded in the Zenodo repository and will be made available in open access under an open license. The decision which data, is made by the project board:

- Data from research platform and benchmarking tools
- Data from Research Impact Literacy Surveys
- Data from repository of Best Practices
- Data collected for the ENLIGHT R&I Observatory
- Data and analysis from the Open Science Surveys

The aim is that all data available on the R&I observatory shall be made publicly available to encourage synergies between ENLIGHT partners and the local actors of the local ecosystems. If possible, the data will be made available under an open license or in the public domain.

Data available on the R&I observatory, will be re-used by the external stakeholders of ENLIGHT. The aim of the tool is also to be available after the end of the project.

Accessible via advanced search for projects (via Grant ID): <https://explore.openaire.eu>

2.2.5 Is an embargo applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents)?

- No

2.2.6 If an embargo is applied (see question 2.2.5), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

Not applicable

2.2.7 Will the data and other research outputs be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?

- Yes

Publicly available outcomes are published in Zenodo, which uses the [OAI-PMH Interface](#).

2.2.8 If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?

To share and store data publicly available, a community is set up on Zenodo.org. Zenodo currently offers a retention period for the lifetime of the repository (20 years, <https://about.zenodo.org/policies/>). In case of closure of the repository, best efforts will be made to integrate all content into suitable alternative institutional and/or subject based repositories.

The data will be deposited in ENLIGHT RISE Share Point (Microsoft 365 Teams) for the confidential data and on the R&I observatory for the public ones and will be stored as long as the ENLIGHT RISE Share-Point is active and the need for the data to be stored.

Detailed information can be found in the data table.

2.2.9 How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

The data stored in the sharepoint environment is managed by University of Bordeaux. The project coordination team allows access to certain institutional accounts upon request of the partners.

At the moment of editing this version of the DMP, the ENLIGHT RISE Project Board is investigating how to address this by the end of and beyond the project.

2.2.10 Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

- Yes

The Project Board acts as a data access committee.

2.2.11 Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why.

- Yes

Metadata of publicly available outcomes in Zenodo is licensed under CC0, except for email addresses. All metadata is exported via OAI-PMH and can be harvested. Information found on the website of Zenodo: <https://about.zenodo.org/policies/>

Metadata of confidential outcomes that are locally stored, are not openly available.

2.2.12 Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?

- No

2.2.13 How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?

To share and store data publicly available, a community is set up on Zenodo.org. Zenodo currently offers a retention period for the lifetime of the repository (20 years, <https://about.zenodo.org/policies/>). In case of closure of the repository, best efforts will be made to integrate all content into suitable alternative institutional and/or subject based repositories.

Data available in the R&I Observatory will be available as long as the ENLIGHT R&I observatory will remain.

The data will be deposited in ENLIGHT RISE Share Point (Microsoft 365 Teams) for the confidential data and on the R&I observatory for the public ones and will be stored as long as the ENLIGHT RISE Share-Point is active and the need for the data to be stored. A preservation plan will be set up by the end of the project.

2.2.14 Will documentation or reference about any software needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

The deliverables contain the necessary information and documentation on the software used and needed to access the data.

2.3 FAIR data: Making data interoperable.

2.3.1 What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

Through Zenodo, the ENLIGHT RISE community uses the standards available in Zenodo: Zenodo's metadata is compliant with [DataCite's Metadata Schema](#) minimum and recommended terms, with a few additional enrichments.

2.3.2 In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies: Will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining, or extending them?

Not applicable

2.3.3 Will your data and other research outputs include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

- Yes

In some activities data is reused and the original source is quoted.

Detailed information can be found in the data table.

2.4 FAIR data: Increase data re-use.

2.4.1 How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use?

The deliverables describe the analysis and methodology used.

2.4.2 Will your data and other research outputs be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data and other research outputs be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

All publicly available outcomes will be licenced with a creative commons licence [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International](#).

2.4.3 Will the data and other research output produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

- Yes

All data published in Zenodo or the ENLIGHT website, including services such as the R&I observatory and the impact repository, will be open for re-use.

2.4.4 Will the provenance of the data and other research outputs be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?

- No

Each deliverable explains the generated or re-used dataset.

2.4.5 Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.

Data quality supporting the deliverables is followed up by the Project Management Board.

3. OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUTS

3.1 Do you have any additional information, that was not addressed in the previous sections, which you wish to provide regarding other research outputs that are generated or re-used throughout the project?

- No

4. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

4.1 What will the costs be for making data and other research outputs FAIR in your project?

Apart from some time by dedicated data stewards and project management, we foresee no other costs.

4.2 How will these be covered?

Partly this is covered by project management costs, partly these are in-kind costs by partners.

4.3 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

The ENLIGHT RISE WP9 will oversee data management and updating the Data Management Plan. The ENLIGHT-RISE Directors' meeting and the Project Board are also the bodies guaranteeing the long-term preservation.

Data will be managed in the ENLIGHT R&I observatory, the ENLIGHT RISE SharePoint and the repository Zenodo.

Data and publications to be made available open access shall be submitted to the project coordination team (PCT) for review and approval before being uploaded in the repository by the project coordinator or the work package leaders. The PCT shall be informed 45 days to review the data / publications and 30 days to provide its feedback.

4.4 How will long term preservation be ensured?

Publicly available data will be preserved in Zenodo. The ENLIGHT RISE Project Board is still investigating the preservation of other outcomes.

5. DATA SECURITY

5.1 What provisions are or will be in place for data security?

Foreseen personal data collection and processing as well as protection measures shall comply with the Regulation 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons about the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (GDPR) and national legislations and with the Data Processing Agreement established between the Gent University and all the ENLIGHT RISE project partners.

Partners collecting confidential data will archive them on secured internal servers and restrict their sharing in compliance with section 10 of the Consortium Agreement.

5.2 Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

The ENLIGHT RISE Project Board is still investigating different options. Publicly available data are safely stored in Zenodo.

6. ETHICS

6.1 Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

The 'ethics requirements' that the project must comply with are listed and included in deliverable **D10.1: Protection of Personal Data (POPD - Requirement No. 1 [6]**.

For the secondary use of data, an explicit confirmation that the data used in the project is publicly available and can be freely used for the purposes of the project must be stated in all deliverables.

GDPR issues may arise, for which we will respect GDPR legislations, also in line with the Data Processing Agreement signed by all the partners.

6.2 Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

- Yes

7. OTHER ISSUES

7.1 Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

National and institutional data protection regulations will be considered.